

FHERITALE GAP ANALYSIS AND TECHNOLOGY NEEDS

The FHERITALE project addresses the growing scientific, technological and societal challenges associated with artificial materials - such as micro- and nanoplastics, bioplastics, plastic additives and metallic particles - across food systems, human health and the environment. These challenges are inherently cross-domain and require coordinated access to advanced analytical services, interoperable data infrastructures and harmonised methodologies. Based on 168 responses to an online survey and additional input gathered during a co-creation workshop, the project has taken the first steps towards identifying priority research and service needs, assessing the readiness of existing technologies and highlighting gaps and barriers that limit their effective use in the food, health and environment domains.

PRIORITY NEEDS

Overall, the distribution of priorities reveals a **strong convergence around a limited set of cross-cutting needs**. A clear hierarchy of concerns lies in the Food and Environment domain (*environmental fate and degradation*, and *sustainable and functional food packaging*) while *Standardization of protocols*, *access to infrastructure*, and *One Health assessment* are consistent cross-domain needs.

TECHNOLOGY AND SERVICES READINESS

Perceived readiness levels emerging from the survey. It builds on the FHERITALE Service Readiness Classification: A) Fully operational and accessible services; B) Available but with limitations; C) Emerging or experimental technologies. The values obtained through desk-based analysis and validated by the RIs are reported on the right (see [zenodo.15554665](https://zenodo.org/record/15554665)). The average perceived readiness index points to **gaps in knowledge and visibility** rather than to a lack of underlying capabilities.

ADDRESSING NEEDS WITH SERVICES

Respondents prioritise **support and training, ease of access, and cost-effectiveness** as the most important features of a new service. These aspects were consistently more important than interoperability or regulatory relevance.

This outcome informs that even mature technologies may fail to generate impact if not embedded within accessible, well-supported and economically viable service models.

GAPS, BARRIERS AND DOMAINS

Taken together, the gap and barrier results suggest that the service ecosystem required by FHERITALE is constrained by a combination of **structural limitations** (access and cost) and **system-level enablers** (knowledge, validation, and interoperability). These findings indicate that service development should not focus only on adding “new techniques”, but also on strengthening the conditions that allow techniques to function as reliable services across Europe.

CLUSTER SUGGESTIONS: INTEGRATED SERVICE SOLUTIONS

The survey results highlight that shared needs are connected not with individual technologies, many of which are already well-established, but with integrating them into end-to-end services that address complex, cross-domain needs. This document provides a strong rationale for developing service clusters understood as coordinated sets of infrastructures, tools, expertise, and support functions that can respond to these needs collectively.

ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING

Scope: Detection of MNPs, fate & degradation, environmental impact
Technologies: FTIR, LC-MS, imaging tools
Users: RIs, regulatory agencies, EU projects

ANALYTICAL & CHARACTERISATION SERVICES

Scope: Chemical analysis, spectrometry, material characterisation
Technologies: LC-MS, FTIR, ICP-MS
Users: Industry, RIs, regulators

TOXICOLOGY & EXPOSURE MODELLING

Scope: PBPK, in vivo/in vitro, One Health assessment
Technologies: PBPK modelling, in vivo tox, omics integrations
Users: Academia, RIs, regulators

BIOLOGICAL MODELS & IN-VITRO SYSTEMS

Scope: Organoids, ex vivo assays, 3D systems
Technologies: 3D organoids, placental perfusion, ex vivo platforms
Users: Research groups, RIs, EU consortia

DATA INTEROPERABILITY & DIGITAL TOOLS

Scope: Image analysis, data integration, FAIR pipelines
Technologies: Digital analysis, AI tools, interoperable platforms
Users: All stakeholder groups

SUSTAINABLE PACKAGING & FUNCTIONAL MATERIALS

Scope: Eco-functional materials, circularity, functional properties
Technologies: Material testing, chemical profiling
Users: Industry, academia, RIs